

A New Entropy Equation for Electrophoresis and Sedimentation Potential and Temperature Dependence of the New Interaction Rate Constant

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New expressions describing the entropy production and the rate equations for electrophoresis and sedimentation potential have been derived by introducing the proportionality constants of the linear laws in the interaction rate constants of the above phenomena. The temperature dependence of the modified interaction rate constant¹, L , thus obtained for acetone/pyrex sinter system, has been analysed and compared with that of the ordinary interaction rate constant, L_{12} . The results are found to be in agreement with P. Van Rysselberghe and in conformity with our previous results.

The interaction rate constants, L_{ik}^s , find their frequent use in thermodynamics of irreversible processes²⁻⁶. These have been a subject matter of great interest for the verification of symmetry relations, in recent years. Precise experiments have been performed for their accurate evaluation in various systems and under different applied forces, *viz.*, temperature gradient⁷ and potential gradient⁸⁻¹¹. Their variations with temperature have also been studied^{7-9,11}, in many systems. The temperature dependence of the L_{ik}^s , thus obtained, has been compared with those of the corresponding modified interaction rate constants¹²⁻¹⁴, L^s , in the same system. Analysis on thermal diffusion¹², electro-osmosis¹³ and thermo-osmosis¹⁴ has established the validity of the theory put forth by P. Van Rysselberghe¹. The present communication aims at writing new expressions describing the entropy production and the new rate equations for electrophoresis and sedimentation potential and analysing the comparative temperature dependence of L_{ik} and L , obtained from the measurements of sedimentation potential in acetone/pyrex sinter system¹¹. The new expressions are derived as discussed under.

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1. P. Van Rysselberghe, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1962, **36**, 1327.
2. I. Prigogine, "Introduction to Thermodynamics of Irreversible Processes", Interscience Publishers, Inc., New York, N.Y., 1961.
3. S. R. de Groot, "Thermodynamics of Irreversible Processes", North-Holland Publishing Company, Amsterdam, 1959.
4. K. M. Jha, *Chemical Processing and Engineering*, 1967, **1**, 98.
5. D. G. Miller, *Chem. Rev.*, 1960, **60**, 15.
6. K. M. Jha and Md. Zakaria, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1970, **8**, 339.
7. R. P. Rastogi, R. L. Blokhra and R. K. Agarwal, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1964, **60**, 1986.
8. R. P. Rastogi and K. M. Jha, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1966, **70**, 1017.
9. R. P. Rastogi and K. M. Jha, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1966, **62**, 585.
10. R. P. Rastogi and B. M. Mishra, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1967, **63**, 584.
11. R. P. Rastogi and B. M. Mishra, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1967, **63**, 2927, 2929.
12. R. P. Rastogi and R. L. Blokhra, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1963, **39**, 241.
13. K. M. Jha, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1968, **6**, 46.
14. K. M. Jha and M. Jha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **45**, 966.

We consider a two component system *viz.*, a neutral fluid between two electrodes in which insoluble particles of a particular size are allowed to fall under gravity. Electrical energy develops at the cost of potential energy of the falling particles and sedimentation current flows. The reverse of this phenomenon may occur giving rise to electrophoresis.

As shown by de Groot, Mazur and Overbeek¹⁵ the entropy production is expressed as

$$T\sigma = \sum_{i=1}^{i=n} J_i^0 X_i \quad \dots (1)$$

where J_i^0 is defined as the absolute flow of matter, of the kind i , per unit area per unit time and may be expressed^{10(a)} as

$$J_i^0 = \rho_i V_i \quad \dots (2)$$

in which ρ_i and V_i represent the density and the velocity of movement of the i th kind of species respectively and T is absolute temperature. In electrophoresis and sedimentation potential X_1 is given^{10(b)} by

$$X_i = e_i E + g (-\text{grad } \mu_i) \quad \dots (3)$$

where e_i is the charge per unit mass of the species i , E is the applied electrical field, g is the gravitational field per unit mass and μ_i is the chemical potential of the species i . At constant temperature eq. (3) reduces^{10(b)} to

$$X_i = e_i E + g (-v_i \text{grad } P) \quad \dots (4)$$

In eq. (4) v_i represents the partial specific volume of the component i , and P refers to pressure. Since the total volume flow through a section vanishes we may write^{10(b)}

$$\sum_{i=1}^{i=n} v_i J_i^0 = 0 \quad \dots (5)$$

For two component systems, therefore, eq. (1) can be written as

$$\sigma = J_1^0 \{e_1 E + (1 - v_1/v_2)g\}/T \quad \dots (6)$$

or

$$\sigma = J_1^0 \{e_1 E + (1 - \rho_2/\rho_1)g\}/T \quad \dots (7)$$

where the subscripts 1 and 2 refer to the particle and medium respectively. In eqs. (6) and (7) our choice for the two fluxes *i.e.*, current density 1 and the mass flow J are defined as

$$I = e_1 J_1^0 \quad \dots (8)$$

$$J = J_1^0 (1 - v_1/v_2) = J_1^0 (1 - \rho_2/\rho_1) \quad \dots (9)$$

The corresponding two forces for these flows are E/T and g/T respectively. Here E/T is the potential gradient which may be written as $\Delta\phi/lT$, where $\Delta\phi$ is the applied potential difference in between the two electrodes held l cm apart.

When $\Delta\phi = 0$, eq. (7) reduces to

$$\sigma_2 = J_1^0(1 - \rho_2/\rho_1)g/T = J_{\Delta\phi=0}(g/T) \quad \dots (10)$$

The phenomenological rate equation obtained from eq. (10) is

$$J_{\Delta\phi=0} = L_{22}X_2 \quad \dots (11)$$

where $(J)_{\Delta\phi=0}$ is the mass flow, per unit cross-sectional area per unit time in absence of any potential gradient, L_{22} is the phenomenological rate constant and X_2 the corresponding force defined by

$$X_2 = (g/T) \quad \dots (12)$$

The sedimentation rate of a particle under the gravitational force g , is governed by the Stoke's Law. If r be the radius of the falling particle through a medium whose viscosity is η , the constant velocity V , with which the particle moves, is given by the equation

$$4/3\pi r^3(\rho_1 - \rho_2)g = 6\pi\eta r V \quad \dots (13)$$

or

$$V = 2/9(\rho_1 - \rho_2)g r^2/\eta \quad \dots (14)$$

Hence J i.e., mass flow per unit area per unit time is given by the product of $(\rho_1 - \rho_2)$ and V . Substituting the above value of V in the expression for J , we obtain

$$J = (\rho_1 - \rho_2)V = 2/9(\rho_1 - \rho_2)^2 r^2 g/\eta \quad \dots (15)$$

Since J , given by equations (11) and (15) are identical and the same quantity having the dimensions $mt^{-2}t^{-1}$, the r.h.s. of these equations are equalities from which we obtain

$$L_{22} = 2/9(\rho_1 - \rho_2)^2 r^2 T/\eta = \alpha(T/\eta) \quad \dots (16)$$

where $\alpha = 2/9(\rho_1 - \rho_2)^2 r^2$ and is a constant for the system under consideration.

In the absence of any applied potential gradient to the system, eq. (7) together with eqs. (9) and (11) is written as

$$\sigma_2 = J_{\Delta\phi=0}(g/T) = L_{22}(g/T)^2 \quad \dots (17)$$

Substituting the value of L_{22} from eq. (16), eq. (17) is written as

$$\sigma_2 = \alpha(T/\eta)(g/T)^2 = \alpha\beta^2 \quad \dots (18)$$

where

$$\beta = gT^{-1/2}\eta^{-1/2} \quad \dots (19)$$

β may be treated as the new force. If the corresponding new flow is recognised as γ then the following equation would be satisfied

$$\sigma_2 = \alpha\beta^2 = \gamma^2/\alpha \quad \dots (20)$$

and the following relation is obtained for the new flux and the corresponding new force

$$\gamma = \alpha\beta \quad \dots (21)$$

Substitution of α in terms of L_{22} , T , η according to eq. (16); β in terms of g , T , η according to eq. (19) and rearranging in terms of J according to eq. (17); eq. (21) is written as

$$\gamma = J\eta^{\frac{1}{2}}T^{-\frac{1}{2}} \quad \dots (22)$$

Further in the absence of the gravitational force when only the potential gradient is operative, eq. (7) can be written as

$$\sigma_1 = J_1^0 e_1 (E/T) = I(\Delta\phi/lT) \quad \dots (23)$$

since $J_1^0 e_1$ describes the current density I . The phenomenological rate equation is given by the expression

$$I = L_{11}X_1; \quad (X_1 = (\Delta\phi/lT)) \quad \dots (24)$$

From Ohm's Law we get

$$L_{11} = \Omega T \quad \dots (25)$$

where Ω represents the conductance of the particle.

Proceeding as before for the evaluation of the new forces and fluxes in respect of current density and applied potential difference we get the following relations

$$\text{new force} = (\Delta\phi/l) \cdot T^{-\frac{1}{2}} \quad \dots (26)$$

$$\text{new flow} = IT^{-\frac{1}{2}} \quad \dots (27)$$

We have so long considered the two situations separately in isolation with the other i.e., when only one force becomes operative through the system. Under the condition when there is interaction we obtain a new expression for entropy production in respect of electrophoresis and sedimentation potential in accordance with the new forces and fluxes for these phenomena as

$$\sigma = \sum_{i=1}^{i=2} J_i X_i = IT^{-\frac{1}{2}} \{ (\Delta\phi/l) T^{-\frac{1}{2}} \} + (J\eta^{\frac{1}{2}} T^{-\frac{1}{2}}) (g\eta^{-\frac{1}{2}} T^{-\frac{1}{2}}) \quad \dots (28)$$

The two new rate equations for the above two phenomena are described by equations (29) and (30)

$$IT^{-\frac{1}{2}} = \Omega (\Delta\phi/l) T^{-\frac{1}{2}} + LgT^{-\frac{1}{2}}\eta^{-\frac{1}{2}} \quad \dots (29)$$

$$J\eta^{\frac{1}{2}} T^{-\frac{1}{2}} = L(\Delta\phi/l) T^{-\frac{1}{2}} + \alpha g T^{-\frac{1}{2}} \eta^{-\frac{1}{2}} \quad \dots (30)$$

In eq. (29) and (30) L is the new and modified interaction rate constant.

The phenomenological rate equations for the two electrokinetic phenomena are accordingly written² as

$$I = L_{11}(\Delta\phi/lT) + L_{12}(g/T) \quad \dots (31)$$

$$J = L_{21}(\Delta\phi/lT) + L_{22}(g/T) \quad \dots (32)$$

where L_{11} , L_{22} are phenomenological rate constants and L_{12} , L_{21} , are interaction rate constants which obey¹⁰ Onsager's reciprocity relation $L_{12} = L_{21}$.

Comparing the coefficients of g in eqs. (29) and (31) we get

$$L = (L_{12}/T)\eta^2 \quad \dots (33)$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The values of L_{12} at different temperatures for the acetone/pyrex sinter system have been taken from the recent experimental data by Rastogi and Mishra¹¹. L has been calculated by using eq. (33). Comparative dependence of L_{12} and L on temperature has been made by using a differential method discussed earlier¹²⁻¹⁴. In the present case $\Delta t = 2^\circ$ has been chosen for the purpose. Results are given in the table and represented in the figure. The validity of Onsager's reciprocity relation has been assumed to hold good even in the case of the modified interaction rate constant¹⁶.

TABLE

Mean Temp(°K)	dL_{12}/L_{12}	dL/L
304	0.119	0.087
306	0.105	0.080
308	0.096	0.074
310	0.088	0.068
312	0.081	0.064
314	0.073	0.060
316	0.069	0.057
318	0.065	0.053

Results are in agreement with P. Van Rysselberghe. The constancy of L is greater than that of L_{12} . This is consistent with our previous observations¹²⁻¹⁴. The average variation of L in the present case is found to be 78.6% of that of L_{12} , the minimum and maximum limits being 73.1% and 82.6% of L_{12} respectively, within the temperature range 304°K-318°K for which the experimental data for L_{12} are available¹¹.

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